

Educating emotions for the 21st century

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Emotional education has occupied a secondary place in Colombian education. Although efforts have been made to educate citizens, institutional efforts have not been sufficient. A balance of the years of the 21st century shows that the rates of violence in the country continue to grow, evidencing a lack of individual and collective control of emotions. This feature is associated with how violence has been inserted into the civilizing process of Colombian society. This article proposes a reflection on the articulation between emotional education and the civilizing process, concretizing the reflection in the Colombian case and proposing a possible alternative for emotional education in the coming decades.

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1. INTRODUCTION

In the annual report on violence in Colombia for 2023 [1], a critical situation is shown in different topics: 188 social leaders and 44 signatories of the peace process were murdered, 94 massacres with a total of 303 victims (being one of the highest figures in the last five years) and 167,540 events of forced displacement, among other data. On the other hand, according to data from the National Institute of Legal Medicine and Forensic Sciences [2] the total number of homicides in 2023 was 14,033 people (almost 5% more than the previous year) and, according to information from the Colombian Observatory of Femicides, in 2023 there were 525 cases of femicides in the country (a figure slightly lower than in 2022, with 557 records).

These figures are an indisputable indicator of the persistence of multidimensional violence in the country in recent years and, at the same time, a demonstration of the failure of public policy aimed at guaranteeing Article 22 of the 1991 Political Constitution, which refers to peace as a right and a duty of obligatory compliance.

Understanding the violence associated with the structural and political factors that have led to the Colombian irregular conflict for more than sixty years has occupied the attention of several researchers and think tanks, whose work has allowed obtaining an extensive and in-depth analytical overview of the issue. It is enough to read, among the vast existing literature, the twelve analytical essays and the two reports prepared by the Historical Commission on the Conflict and its Victims [3] to confirm the important state of progress of academic reflection in this field.

However, beyond the understanding of structural and political factors, at least one piece of the puzzle is still missing to answer the question: why do Colombians continue to see violence as a valid and recurring political and social practice? In my opinion, the answer to this question cannot be found exclusively in macro factors, but there are also elements of the civilizing process (in Eliasian terms) and of the education of emotions that can help us understand why violence has become internalized in our social being as a legitimate practice of socialization. Below, I will present some elements around these questions.

2. REFLECTION

The social subject has an integral character. In its formation, there are elements of an economic nature (associated with the search for its reproduction and well-being), political (need to participate in public life), cultural (recognition of individual and collective practices), and spiritual (self-knowledge of the self that gives meaning to vital existence). These topics, in my opinion, are crossed by two fundamental aspects in the construction of subjectivity: how we process emotions and how we relate and build interdependencies with others. Below, I will make a brief theoretical reference to these two aspects to provide, a posteriori, elements of analysis for the Colombian case, and the permanence of violence in our social life.

2.1 Educating emotions

Emile Durkheim published [4] in which he proposed a type of facts that, being external to the individual, have such a coercive power that they impose themselves on his way of acting. It may seem anachronistic to return to these analyses that are more than a century old, however, I wish to recover Durkheim's reflective intention on how some facts, social ones, acquire a degree of prestige that ends up imposing themselves as beliefs and practices, that is, becoming institutionalized in social life.

In the prologue to the second edition, the author expands on this idea by noting that the relationship we establish with institutions is dialectical: at the same time that social norms are imposed on us, we end up clinging to them; we are coerced, but we end up accepting and recognizing the convenience of this coercion. This process of coercion takes place, for the French sociologist, in the settings of socialization (primary and secondary).

Now, one of the characteristics of contemporary times understood as a period of constant changes (the advent of the Internet, the prevalence of social networks, increasing individualization, among others) rather

than as a chronologically defined historical period, is the growing pressure on the spaces of socialization characteristic of modernity. The family, the school, and local communities, to mention just a few, are not the main reference for the creation and diffusion of collective habits. However, traditions, customs, ways of being, and making society travel in our present along paths quite different from those of five or six decades ago. As noted above, [5] Society exists in the activities of individualization, that is, beyond being a collective project, society takes shape in the renegotiation of the mutual entanglements of everyday life. In this scenario, how can we demand that children's emotions be educated in traditional spaces of socialization?

Almost five centuries ago a European thinker (Erasmus of Rotterdam) sent a book to the press (*De civilitate morum puerilium*) which had a deeply pragmatic objective: to educate the manners of children. Perhaps this was the first manual of urbanity of modernity and was aimed at defining some elementary activities to regulate the behavior and expression of emotions of people in society. Here we ask ourselves, is it possible to educate the forms of affectivity, understanding it as a feeling towards another person? If this possibility is real, then we can accept that feelings are socially constructed, that is, an I love you does not have the same content in the 20th century as in the Middle Ages, venture a historical period.

To love, to want, since the 18th century implies a logic of care, of protection, of the preservation of social ties in the family, and then in other instances of socialization. What is the meaning of love today? As suggested in [6], love is a liquid, ephemeral expression. In a society in which consumerism is the reference of social prestige and material and spiritual progress, human beings have become products that are consumed and whose wrappers are thrown everywhere recurrently. We could be in a moment of what is called the bankruptcy of Eros to express the boredom and misfortune that love produces in us [7].

Faced with this process of individualization, different societies have adopted measures aimed at reestablishing trust and community ties, as well as educating citizens to change this reality by generating more empathy and solidarity.

Thus, thinking about emotions inevitably implies thinking about the forms (behaviors, norms, customs) on which society itself is constituted. To do so, it is necessary to keep at least two premises in mind: first, the content of emotions changes over time, for example, shame in the Middle Ages could be associated with introspection and reflection (positive connotation), while in the present era it can be related to a problem of isolation and insecurity (negative connotation); second, the producers of emotions also change depending on the era (what produces joy, fear or disgust in a specific society?)

What repels a 20th-century Japanese may be very different from what repels a 21st-century Colombian. Beyond entering into the debate on the existence of emotional communities or emotional regimes [8] what I wish to underline is the complexity of emotional education in the present and, in turn, the need to understand the importance of the emotional dimension in the structuring of the social, if you will, of social facts. Emotions are not only those spasmodic manifestations of sensation or feeling that arise as a response to external stimuli but the bedrock on which a large part, if not all, of our cultural and social life, is built [9].

2.2 The civilizing process

Understanding this category implies stating two premises: first, the place of the civilizing process is culture; second, the nature of the human being is violent. In this direction, the effort of different societies to channel, control, contain, or guide violence is associated with the action that culture exerts on individuals. Individuals are not automatic mechanisms that act mechanically in response to an order external to their daily experience. On the contrary, in every social relationship individuals have specific interests that express reasons and objectives that they wish to fulfill when they establish a relationship with other human beings. These relationships promoted by specific interests are what Elias calls figurations: different social fabrics that individuals create with their interactions in every one of the spaces that shape a society [10].

Placing this reflection on a diachronic plane, the order that characterizes the civilizing process comes from the interdependence of human beings, understood as a network of relationships that is historically woven between individuals. In more stable societies, the order represented in the State will have its counterpart in

an apparatus of individual self-control whose operation is almost automatic and guarantees that subjects do not transgress what is established and socially accepted. In his words:

The monopoly of physical violence, and the concentration of weapons and armed men in one place makes the exercise of violence more or less calculable and forces unarmed men in pacified areas to restrain themselves using foresight and reflection. In a word, this monopolistic organization forces human beings to accept a more or less intense form of self-control [11].

Understanding the civilizing process requires a long-term view, that is, the form that interdependencies between human beings take, that is, the characteristics of the relationships and social and emotional bonds between individuals in any society, are anchored in the long term. Behaviors, attitudes, customs, gestures, etc. depend on how societies have shaped them over time. In this direction, Elias' proposal suggests that social regulations, as well as individual modes of action, their contents, and their forms and transformations, can only be investigated and adequately understood if our considerations include, as a central element, the long-term development of historical-social processes over centuries [12].

What is the relationship between the civilizing process and emotions? Elias' sociology can be understood as a sociology of affections, insofar as the long process of the constitution of society necessarily passes through the permanent adjustment of the individual's self-control mechanisms, which establish the individual's commitment or distancing from a certain emotional situation. Let's see: [...] the notion of commitment measures the degree to which a person is affected - interested, moved, touched - by the outside world that manifests itself in the form of a living being (human or animal), an object (a work of art), a social phenomenon (a manifestation) or a natural phenomenon (a storm) [13]. That is to say, how an individual responds to a situation in which he is involved depends closely on how the self-control mechanisms have been constituted in the society to which he belongs.

Far from thinking of the relationship between individual and society from a structuralist perspective, in which the former is automatically subject to the norms imposed by the latter, we consider that the relationship is dialectical. In the same way that society transforms the particular characteristics of the individual, the latter can transform the cultural patterns of society, which can be understood if we assume that one of the peculiarities of man is the fact that by nature he can change in a specific way. His integration into society eloquently shows this [14]. The biological and psychic peculiarities that allow the variability of human behavior are transformed, in turn, by the same development of human societies over time.

In this direction, the concept of *homo clausus* (the bourgeoisie or the proletariat, for example) loses relevance compared to the notion of *homines aperti*, which is a historical and interdependent being, since, following the Eliasian theses, the life of the human being must be understood as a being with others that is dynamically transformed depending on the flows of power [15]. There is no abstract domination before human experience, but it is precisely this experience that gives rise to the forms of control, subjection, and social negotiation.

2.3 Emotions, civilization, and violence in Colombia

So far we have referred to two aspects: 1) emotions change over time and vary from one social setting to another; 2) the education of emotions is closely related to the civilizing process of a given community. Below, we propose an approach to anchoring these elements in the Colombian case.

After the promulgation of the 1991 Constitution, the need to form a citizen in harmony with modern democracy became the center of the debate. Education for democracy gained unusual importance and gradually became civic education, ending in the need to develop civic skills. Without going into an analysis of the course of this decade of uncertainties, a task that we did in another work [16], I wish to focus on the proposal of the national government to standardize civic education.

In a very optimistic way, Guide No. 6 was called: Citizenship Training... Yes, it is possible! This emphatic announcement, with exclamation marks, dates back to 2004, and, twenty years later, it would be good to evaluate the impact of this policy. Do we have better citizens today than two decades ago? Have the rates of violence (school and social) been reduced? Have we built a more tolerant society? In the presentation of the

booklet, the minister of the time said: We are convinced that education is one of the paths that will make peace possible. If we open the doors of all schools and colleges to Colombian boys and girls and, in addition, provide quality education to each one of them, we will not only be keeping them away from poverty but also allowing them to live and build a country in peace [17].

However, the implementation of this praiseworthy ideal had more obstacles and shortcomings than virtues and achievements. The ineffectiveness of the standards of civic competencies instrumentalized the political and moral formation of boys and girls through a cognitive evolutionary approach, turning citizenship into a matter of evaluation, and did not achieve the main objective of the policy: to create democratic environments within the framework of respect, defense, and promotion of human rights. The standards left out emotional education and focused on a rationalist view of moral education, leaving aside the approach to passions and emotions. Contrary to this bet, a recognition of the Colombian civilizing process would have shown the need to start from the tragedy produced by the overflow of passions, recognizing our *kinetic inclination*. [18] and, from there, propose profound cultural changes, which have nothing to do with the evaluation of a standard of coexistence.

By instrumentalizing civic education in schools, an abstract, archetypal universe was created, in which boys and girls developed certain skills by their mental age. Perhaps what Jaramillo, Ochoa and Chau, and the other advisors of this policy, forgot is that children live in real moral conditions of existence, that in their neighborhoods violence is present on every corner, and that their families, when they have them, revolve around discriminatory, exclusionary and unpleasant practices that are very far from the moral state desired by the Ministry. A couple of data that show part of this reality are the following: first, domestic violence, according to Legal Medicine, increased between 2021 and 2022 by about 23%; second, according to data from the Laboratory of Economics of Education of the Pontificia Universidad Javeriana (May 2022), Colombia is the country with the second highest rate of school bullying among the Latin American countries that make up the OECD. I could suggest that, in a real country, which did not consider Guide No. 6 of the Ministry of Education, the civilizing process advances through other channels.

The issue is not exhausted, nor should it be, in school or educational policies. To problematize a little our process of moral formation and install it in a broader scenario, it is necessary to point out some aspects of our social ethos. First of all, it is necessary to recognize that the monopoly of force and violence does not belong to the State. Far from the thesis [19] according to which the State is a human community that successfully claims the monopoly of legitimate violence, in our country different groups have appeared that, in the name of the most diverse causes and justifications, exercise violence.

From the peasant self-defense groups of the 1930s, some of which would be the basis of the communist guerrillas of the 1960s, through to the multiple expressions of the armed left, the paramilitary groups of the 1990s, to the drug cartels, violence has been exercised outside of state control, and in some cases, with its connivance. The State has so little control over the use of violence that since the 1980s multiple expressions of urban violence have appeared that have had a multidimensional character (a very convenient expression used by some sociologists to hide their inability to fully understand the phenomenon).

The other ingredient I wish to refer to is that of psychic control of emotions. As I noted earlier, human nature is endowed with an instinctive component regulated by our desires and passions, and it is normal to want to satisfy our desires to achieve physical and mental balance. However, a mechanism of psychic control is built socially, coercion in Eliasian terms, which prevents these passions from overflowing. In our case, the family, the school, and much less the political sphere have been able to establish a pattern of control of our emotions.

It seems that we live on the edge, in an all-or-nothing situation, and that is why we refuse to say no as an answer to our requests. The citizen who commits a traffic violation ends up bribing the authority when his plea is not heeded, the young man steals a kiss from the girl who says she does not feel reciprocated, the soccer player reprimands the referee after not heeding his complaint... and so on, we could list countless situations in everyday life that would demonstrate this lack of emotional control, which is reinforced by the

messianic character of political leaders who, anchored in the atmosphere of the cold war, continue to preach the octogenarian maxim: he who is not with me, is against me.

A third element that I wish to highlight is the lack of peaceful areas. Since the 1950s, the governments in power have advanced negotiation processes with armed groups. Since the constitutional reform of 1991, talks have been held, some more successful than others, with the M-19, the EPL, Manuel Quintín Lame, paramilitary groups, and, most recently, with the FARC-EP. However, each process leaves dissident offspring who are nourished by the absence of a monopoly on violence by the State and come to have a power that makes them worthy of a new negotiation.

The current government, for example, is determined to achieve what it has called total peace by making concessions to the FARC dissidents, which now number more than 30 fronts, each with autonomy and territorial control, to the ELN, to the Clan del Golfo, among other Gaos (a lexical euphemism to name in different ways emerging political-military phenomena inherited from previous violence). In short, despite its efforts, Colombian society has not been able to build peaceful environments and, on the contrary, violent conflict has become embedded in the smallest spaces of socialization.

The reference to these three elements allows me to suggest that violence in the country is part of the constitutive experience of our society, that is, rather than being considered a dysfunctional manifestation of our community life, it is an integral part of it, and I would even dare to say that it is violence that underlies our collective experience. In the same way that violence is linked to our experience of political and democratic order, I suggest that it is also organically intertwined with our social being and is the route by which social orders are built [20].

3. CONCLUSIONS

We have focused our reflection on the formation of the subject on two important components: the education of emotions and their relationship with the civilizing process. I consider it key to emphasize that, in the historical analyses of the constitution of Colombian subjectivity, the subject of emotions and affectivity has not had a central place. History has dealt with subjects that, in the opinion of academics, are more structural (formation of the State, agrarian problem, development of capitalism, etc.), overlooking the role played by the affective dimension of the subject and emotional education in the development of the civilizing process in one sense or another.

In general terms, we have seen how, in a broad sense, the country has seen a game between order and violence that has given rise to a particular political experience in which aggression against the adversary, even its elimination, is legitimized by the social order. At the same time, the political and moral education of children and young people has been instrumentalized under the Teflon of a psychologizing position that bets on the development of civic competencies of abstract social subjects, existing only in the minds of the intellectuals and politicians who have led this field.

Here it is essential to underline a first conclusion concerning the imperative obligation to look at historical development integrally. Emotions and social structures are two sides of a coin, which cannot be understood without seeing both sides of it. Neither emotions can be understood without taking into account the structural dimension of the social, nor can objective material reality be interpreted if the production of the affective life of subjects is not brought into play. [21]. The first call, then, is for the academy and consists of suggesting the formation of comprehensive views (if you will, inter and transdisciplinary) that allow a global understanding of historical and social processes.

A second conclusion is directed at schools and education professionals. How are emotions being taught in educational institutions? What values are encouraged beyond compliance or non-compliance with the standards defined by the Ministry of National Education? What place do empathy, solidarity, and recognition of others have within the educational processes? The initial balance seems unflattering. Colombia continues to be a violent country with its children and young people. Exclusion, abuse, and the lack of satisfaction of

the basic needs of minors (education, food, recreation, etc.) continue to be high, and the problems of educational institutions seem to overwhelm the capacity of teachers to create alternative solutions.

In a beautiful text published with the chronological opening of the 21st century, the teacher Sábato called for the need to recover some values as a key piece to recover the sense of humanity. The feeling of orphanhood so present in this time is due to the fall of shared and sacred values. If values are relative, and one adheres to them like the regulations of a sports club, how can they save us from misfortune or misfortune? This is how so many desperate people end up on the verge of suicide, and that is why loneliness becomes so terrible and overwhelming [22]. For this reason, almost poetically, Sábato proposes that we rescue dignity, selflessness, and stoicism within the collective experience.

A third reflection that I propose is anchored in the incorporation of the education of emotions as a central aspect of the educational processes of the coming decades. This education, which cannot be measured with massive standardized tests, is fundamental in the construction of a new subject and, therefore, of a civilizing process in which violence is not a legitimate strategy of action. This education implies decentering the educational act from its Apollonian perspective from which to form reason and giving way to the Dionysian, the passionate, the affective. It is about creating a politics of life, allied to any form of partisan instrumentalization of any kind, where the axiological and ethical potential of daily life is recognized. This politics is concerned not with politicizing, in the strictest sense of the term, decisions about lifestyle, but with remoralizing them. More precisely, it is about bringing to the surface the moral and existential glimpses rejected from everyday life by the hijacking of experience [23].

This route would allow for an identification, and perhaps a greater understanding, of the specificities of emotions and how they are constructed in contemporary educational processes. In addition, it would support the recovery of the agonistic component of community life, making conflict a fundamental part of everyday school life and the processing of this conflict a process in which the germ of the change that society requires can be found.

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